

Placenta Accreta: First Trimester Ultrasonographic Finding. Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Placenta accreta spectrum (PAS) is a potentially life-threatening obstetric complication characterized by abnormal trophoblastic invasion into the myometrium. While prenatal diagnosis is typically made in the second or third trimester, this case reports a suggestive sonographic detection in the first trimester, making it an uncommon clinical finding and an emerging diagnostic insight in the current medical literature. It provides evidence for the possibility of early suspicion of PAS, even in the absence of regular prenatal care, and highlights the utility of Doppler ultrasound in early pregnancy.

Case report: A 32-year-old woman, G3C1A1, with a history of cesarean section due to breech presentation and uterine curettage following spontaneous abortion, was at 13.2 weeks of gestation without formal prenatal control. Two weeks prior to hospital admission, a transvaginal ultrasound revealed an irregular myometrial-placental interface, scar fibrosis in the lower uterine segment, multiple tortuous subplacental venous lakes with irregular Doppler flow, a live fetus with a heart rate of 145 bpm, and an open cervix—findings highly suggestive of PAS. The patient later presented to the emergency department with active vaginal bleeding, moderate pelvic pain, and general malaise. On physical examination, she exhibited tachycardia, normal remaining vital signs, active trans-cervical bleeding, and cervical dilation. Due to the persistent bleeding and prior suggestive imaging findings, placenta accreta was considered the main diagnosis. A multidisciplinary consensus led to obstetric hysterectomy.

The procedure was performed under epidural anesthesia and revealed hematogenous infiltration of the myometrium and macroscopic signs of PAS in the lower uterine segment and cervix. Estimated blood loss was 300 ml, and a Penrose drain was placed. The surgery was uneventful. The patient had a favorable postoperative course, was discharged after 48 hours, and attended follow-up for pathology review, which confirmed placenta accreta with insertion over the endocervical canal.

Conclusion: This case illustrates that sonographic signs suggestive of PAS can be present as early as the first trimester, particularly in patients with risk factors such as prior cesarean delivery or uterine curettage. Early recognition through Doppler ultrasound, even without formal prenatal care, enabled rapid and effective therapeutic decision-making, reducing potential complications. Multidisciplinary management and appropriate surgical planning were key to a favorable maternal outcome. This report reinforces the need for active clinical suspicion and targeted imaging in at-risk patients during early pregnancy.

KEYWORDS: Placenta, placenta accreta spectrum, first trimester, obstetric hysterectomy, Doppler ultrasound

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INTRODUCTION

Placenta accreta spectrum (PAS) is a general term used to describe abnormal trophoblastic invasion into the myometrium and sometimes extending to or beyond the serosa. It is clinically relevant because the placenta fails to separate spontaneously during delivery, and attempts at manual extraction can result in life-threatening hemorrhage, often requiring hysterectomy. Most cases of PAS are thought to result from placental implantation in areas of defective decidualization due to pre-existing damage at the endometrial-myometrial interface.¹

Placenta accreta is one of the leading causes of obstetric hemorrhage. Immediate complications include postpartum hemorrhage and related conditions such as disseminated intravascular coagulation, multiorgan dysfunction and/or failure, and death.² The global incidence of placenta accreta is not precisely known, as it is a histopathological diagnosis and not all cases are managed with hysterectomy. However, its incidence is increasing in developed countries, mainly due to the rising frequency of cesarean sections.³

The most important risk factor for PAS is placenta previa following a previous cesarean delivery. Other risk factors include prior uterine surgery with endometrial disruption (e.g., cavity-penetrating myomectomy, hysteroscopic resection of intrauterine adhesions or fibroids, cornual resection of ectopic pregnancy, dilation and curettage, endometrial ablation), maternal age >35 years, multiparity, history of pelvic radiation, manual extraction of the placenta, postpartum endometritis, infertility and/or infertility treatments, and multiple gestations.⁴⁻⁵

The main diagnostic modality is obstetric ultrasound, with transvaginal ultrasound and color Doppler being the most frequently used tools. In selected cases, magnetic resonance imaging may complement the assessment to evaluate the extent of placental invasion.⁶

The objective of this article is to present a case of placenta accreta diagnosed by first-trimester ultrasound, managed by obstetric hysterectomy due to persistent active bleeding.

CASE REPORT

A 32-year-old urban resident woman, with a secondary school education, housewife, G3 C1 A1, with a history of cesarean delivery due to breech presentation and a first-trimester spontaneous abortion requiring uterine curettage. She had no relevant family or personal medical history, and no history of chronic diseases, smoking, alcohol use, or medication. She was 13.2 weeks pregnant according to first-trimester ultrasound and had not received prenatal care.

Two weeks before hospital admission, a transvaginal ultrasound showed a uterus with preserved morphology, irregular myometrial-placental interface in the lower uterine segment, and fibrotic scarring consistent with a previous cesarean section. The implantation site was located in this scarred area. Multiple tortuous subplacental vascular lakes

with irregular flow were identified on color Doppler. A single live fetus was observed with a heart rate of 145 bpm, gestational sac with adequate decidual reaction, and an open cervix with internal os dilation of 2.6 mm and external os of 1–7 mm, with high suspicion of trophoblastic invasion (Figure 1).

Two weeks later, the patient was transported by paramedics to the obstetric emergency department due to active, heavy vaginal bleeding, moderate pelvic pain, and general malaise. On physical exam: tachycardia (HR 112 bpm), blood pressure 110/70 mmHg, mild mucocutaneous pallor, afebrile. Abdomen was soft and non-tender. Active vaginal bleeding with a dilated cervix and abundant clots was observed on vaginal examination, with uterine height estimated at 12 cm on bimanual exam.

A complete blood count showed hemoglobin of 10.4 g/dL. No further imaging was obtained due to the clinical urgency and lack of immediate access to advanced studies. The patient was treated at a public hospital without access to MRI. Initial differential diagnoses included threatened abortion and inevitable abortion; however, the persistent bleeding and prior ultrasound findings suggested PAS. Hydatidiform mole was ruled out due to the absence of vesicular appearance or abnormal β -hCG levels. Prognosis in such cases depends on the extent of placental invasion and timing of diagnosis. Early diagnosis likely prevented severe complications such as hypovolemic shock or the need for massive transfusion.

Given the ultrasound findings highly suggestive of placenta accreta, and following multidisciplinary consensus, an abdominal total hysterectomy under epidural anesthesia was performed. Tranexamic acid (1 g IV) and ceftriaxone (1 g IV) were administered as prophylaxis. Conservative management was not considered due to persistent bleeding, cervical dilation, and completed parity. Intraoperative findings included hemorrhagic infiltration of the myometrium and macroscopic signs of PAS in the lower uterine segment and cervix (Figure 2). Estimated blood loss was 300 mL. A Penrose drain was placed in the pelvic cavity. The surgical plan remained unchanged, and there were no intraoperative complications.

The patient remained hemodynamically stable during and after surgery. No postoperative complications or adverse events occurred. She was hospitalized for 48 hours without incident; the drain was removed 24 hours postoperatively, and she was discharged with outpatient follow-up. At follow-up, the patient reported feeling calm and grateful for the care received. She understood and accepted that the procedure resulted in loss of fertility.

Histopathological analysis reported a total hysterectomy specimen measuring 9.2 x 7.6 x 2.5 cm, with placenta implanted over the internal cervical os, consistent with placenta accreta.

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FIGURE 1: Hypervascularization demonstrated with color Doppler flowmetry.

FIGURE 2: Macroscopic finding of placental accreta.

DISCUSSION

The placenta accreta spectrum (PAS) includes placenta accreta, increta, and percreta—classifications that vary according to the depth of trophoblastic invasion beyond the basal decidua.¹ Its incidence has significantly increased in recent decades, mainly due to rising cesarean section rates and other uterine interventions.⁵ Placenta accreta represents the mildest form and is most frequently diagnosed incidentally, while more severe cases may be associated with massive hemorrhage, the need for hysterectomy, and significant maternal morbidity.¹³

In this case, the patient presented with major risk factors for PAS, including a history of cesarean section and uterine curettage. The condition was incidentally diagnosed in the

first trimester by transvaginal ultrasound; however, due to the absence of prenatal care, she sought medical attention at a later stage.

Ultrasound diagnosis has proven to be a key tool in the early identification of PAS. Although findings are more commonly observed in the second and third trimesters, some signs can be detected as early as the first trimester, especially in patients with known risk factors.¹⁴ Early sonographic signs include gestational sac implantation in the anterior lower uterine segment—often at the site of a cesarean scar—loss of the retroplacental hypoechoic zone, presence of intraplacental vascular lacunae, and disruption of the myometrial-placental interface.⁹

Comstock and collaborators have documented that when these early signs are combined with Doppler evaluation, diagnostic sensitivity improves, even from 6 to 9 weeks of gestation.⁹ Color Doppler allows visualization of abnormal subplacental vascularization and turbulent lacunar flow, which are highly suggestive of PAS—as observed in this case.

The sensitivity of ultrasound to detect PAS increases significantly when targeted at women with known risk factors—such as prior cesarean deliveries, uterine curettage, or myomectomy—and when performed by an experienced operator. Cali and D'Antonio have emphasized the utility of first-trimester screening protocols for women with uterine scars, which could facilitate safer perinatal planning and reduce morbidity associated with late diagnosis.^{10, 11}

Management in suspected PAS cases depends on the degree of placental invasion, the patient's hemodynamic stability, and reproductive plans.⁶⁻⁸ In our patient's case, management took place at a secondary-level facility with access to obstetric intensive care and multiple subspecialties. Given the persistent active vaginal bleeding, the patient's completed parity, and the sonographic findings suggestive of PAS, an obstetric hysterectomy was decided upon following multidisciplinary consensus. Surgery proceeded without complications, with estimated blood loss of 300 mL, and histopathology confirmed placenta accreta.

Current ACOG and FIGO guidelines recommend that PAS be managed in specialized maternal care centers by experienced multidisciplinary teams. Cesarean hysterectomy with the placenta left in situ is the most accepted approach to avoid severe complications such as obstetric hemorrhage.^{6, 11}

In recent years, conservative management strategies have been explored in selected patients—particularly those desiring future fertility, who are hemodynamically stable and without active bleeding. Techniques include focal excision, intra-arterial balloon placement, or intentional placental retention with close surveillance.¹² However, these strategies should be limited to centers with extensive experience and carefully selected patients, which did not apply in this case.

This case highlights the importance of early sonographic evaluation in patients with risk factors for PAS, such as previous cesarean section or uterine curettage. Timely

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detection allows for appropriate management planning and can improve maternal and perinatal outcomes.

Strengths of this case include the early incidental identification of PAS via transvaginal ultrasound and color Doppler, the prompt multidisciplinary approach, surgical decision-making based on clinical stability and obstetric history, and the availability of appropriate hospital resources. Surgical resolution was successful, with no major complications, and histopathological confirmation was obtained.

One important limitation was the lack of prenatal care during the first trimester, which prevented serial sonographic monitoring and advanced therapeutic planning. Additionally, as a single case report, its generalizability to other clinical settings is limited, and diagnostic images or long-term postoperative follow-up are not available. From a medical literature perspective, this case provides supporting evidence for the findings described by Comstock et al., who emphasized the usefulness of Doppler in detecting early signs of placental invasion. It also aligns with FIGO and ACOG recommendations that prioritize maternal safety through surgical management in specialized centers using a multidisciplinary approach.

The conclusions are justified based on clinical and sonographic correlation, appropriate surgical management according to international guidelines, and histopathological confirmation. Early detection allowed for timely intervention, which likely helped prevent major hemorrhage and life-threatening surgical complications. This case contributes to the literature as an illustrative example of placenta accreta spectrum diagnosed in the first trimester and successfully managed with hysterectomy.

CONCLUSION

Placenta accreta is a severe obstetric complication associated with maternal morbidity and mortality. Early prenatal diagnosis, preferably during the first trimester, allows for adequate surgical planning and improves maternal and perinatal outcomes, considering the main risk factors associated with PAS.

Transvaginal ultrasound is the diagnostic tool of choice, and its sensitivity increases when combined with maternal risk factors. Management should be multidisciplinary, with a surgical strategy tailored to the patient's hemodynamic status, fertility desires, and the severity of placental invasion. Obstetric hysterectomy is the most accepted treatment in confirmed cases, especially in patients without fertility preservation desire. Timely detection enables proper management planning and may significantly improve maternal and perinatal outcomes.

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ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS: The patient was fully informed at all times about the diagnosis, procedures performed, and potential risks. Written informed consent was obtained for the surgical and anesthetic procedures, as well as for the publication of this case report, in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and the institutional guidelines of the hospital.

REFERENCIAS

- I. American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists, & Society for Maternal-Fetal Medicine. (2018). Obstetric care consensus No. 7: Placenta accreta spectrum. *Obstetrics & Gynecology*, 132(6), e259–e275. <https://doi.org/10.1097/AOG.0000000000002983>
- II. Cali, G., Giambanco, L., Puccio, G., Forlani, F., Minneci, G., & Valenti, O. (2013). Morbidly adherent placenta: Evaluation of ultrasound diagnostic criteria and differentiation of placenta accreta from percreta. *Ultrasound in Obstetrics & Gynecology*, 41(4), 406–412.
- III. Carusi, D. A., Fox, K. A., Lyell, D. J., Perlman, N. C., Aalipour, S., Einerson, B. D., ... & Belfort, M. A. (2020). Placenta accreta spectrum without placenta previa. *Obstetrics & Gynecology*, 136(3), 458–465. <https://doi.org/10.1097/AOG.0000000000003970>
- IV. Comstock, C. H., Lee, W., Vettraino, I. M., & Bronsteen, R. A. (2003). The early sonographic appearance of placenta accreta. *Journal of Ultrasound in Medicine*, 22(1), 19–23. <https://doi.org/10.7863/jum.2003.22.1.19>
- V. Eller, A. G., Porter, T. F., Soisson, P., & Silver, R. M. (2009). Optimal management strategies for placenta accreta. *BJOG: An International Journal of Obstetrics & Gynaecology*, 116(5), 648–654.
- VI. Flores-Rosas, E. M., Blancas-Camacho, D. E., Casillas-Barrera, M., Solórzano-Aguilar, M., Hernández-Hernández, V. Y., & Ramírez-Urbe, R. D. (2021). Acretismo placentario en el primer trimestre del embarazo como causa de choque hipovolémico: Reporte de un caso. *Ginecología y Obstetricia de México*, 89(11), 913–917. <https://doi.org/10.24245/gom.v89i11.102438>
- VII. García-de la Torre, J. I., González-Cantú, G., Rodríguez-Valdéz, A., Mujica-Torres, A., Villa-Ponce, D., & Aguilar-Zamudio, J. (2018). Acretismo

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- placentario con abordaje predictivo y preventivo de hemorragia obstétrica. *Ginecología y Obstetricia de México*, 86(6), 357–367
<https://doi.org/10.24245/gom.v86i6.2034>
- VIII. Jauniaux, E., Ayres-de-Campos, D., Langhoff-Roos, J., Fox, K. A., Collins, S. L., Duncombe, G., ... & FIGO Placenta Accreta Diagnosis and Management Expert Consensus Panel. (2019). FIGO classification for the clinical diagnosis of placenta accreta spectrum disorders. *International Journal of Gynecology & Obstetrics*, 146(1), 20–24.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/ijgo.12761>
- IX. Miller, D. A., Chollet, J. A., & Goodwin, T. M. (1997). Clinical risk factors for placenta previa–placenta accreta. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 177(1), 210–214.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0002-9378\(97\)70463-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0002-9378(97)70463-0)
- X. Sentilhes, L., Ambroselli, C., Kayem, G., Le Touze, A., Perrotin, F., Fernandez, H., ... & Marpeau, L. (2010). Maternal outcome after conservative treatment of placenta accreta. *Obstetrics & Gynecology*, 115(3), 526–534.
- XI. Sichitiu, J., El-Tani, Z., Mathevet, P., & Desseauve, D. (2021). Conservative surgical management of placenta accreta spectrum: A pragmatic approach. *Journal of Investigative Surgery*, 34(2), 172–180. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08941939.2019.1623956>
- XII. Silver, R. M., Fox, K. A., Barton, J. R., Abuhamad, A. Z., Simhan, H., Huls, C. K., ... & Wright, J. D. (2015). Center of excellence for placenta accreta. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 212(5), 561–568.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajog.2014.11.018>
- XIII. Silver, R. M., Landon, M. B., Rouse, D. J., Leveno, K. J., Spong, C. Y., Thom, E. A., ... & National Institute of Child Health and Human Development Maternal–Fetal Medicine Units Network. (2006). Maternal morbidity associated with multiple repeat cesarean deliveries. *Obstetrics & Gynecology*, 107(6), 1226–1232.
<https://doi.org/10.1097/01.AOG.0000219750.79480.84>
- XIV. Stirnemann, J. J., Mousty, E., Chalouhi, G., Salomon, L. J., Bernard, J. P., & Ville, Y. (2011). Screening for placenta accreta at 11–14 weeks of gestation. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 205(6), 547.e1–547.e6.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajog.2011.07.039>